

Clojure Smells Relevance Survey

Hello!

We are researchers from the **Federal University of Campina Grande (UFCG)**, and we are conducting a study on **code smells in the Clojure ecosystem**. Our goal is to better understand how the community perceives certain code patterns that may indicate issues related to maintainability, clarity, or performance.

To do this, we are collecting feedback from **Clojure practitioners** like you on the smells we identified based on forum discussions, repositories, and real-world code analysis.

The **full catalog**, including methodology, sources, descriptions, and code examples for each smell, is available at:

👉 github.com/nufuturo-ufcg/clj-smells-catalog

In the survey, we ask you to evaluate **21 code smells** in total:

- **12 Clojure-specific smells** (on page 2)
- **9 functional smells** (on page 3), common across functional languages

For each smell, please indicate whether you consider it relevant. Optional comments are welcome.

Completing the survey should take **no more than 20 minutes**.

Thank you very much for your contribution!

Further contributions are also welcome directly on GitHub via Issues or Pull Requests.

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

1. How much experience do you have with Clojure? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- I've never used it
- I'm a beginner (less than 1 year)
- Intermediate (1–3 years)
- Experienced (3–5 years)
- Expert (more than 5 years)

2. GitHub username (optional):

3. Country (optional):

Clojure-specific Smells

These are 12 code smells that arise from idioms, features, or common practices specific to the Clojure language and its ecosystem.

4. **Direct usage of clojure.lang.RT**

This code smell occurs when Clojure code directly invokes methods from the `clojure.lang.RT` class, such as `clojure.lang.RT/iter`, to perform operations that are not exposed through the public Clojure API. The RT class is part of Clojure's internal implementation and is not intended for direct use in application code.

Directly invoking methods from this class can lead to fragile code that is susceptible to breakage with future updates to the language.

Is this smell relevant in your opinion?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes

No

I don't know

5. Comment - Direct usage of clojure.lang.RT
(Optional)

6. **Improper Emptiness Check**

This code smell occurs when developers use verbose or less idiomatic constructs —such as `(not (empty? x))`—to determine whether a collection is non-empty, instead of leveraging the more concise and expressive idiom `(seq x)`. In Clojure, the concept of emptiness is nuanced: `nil` is considered empty, sequences can be infinite or lazy, and realization may matter. Using `seq` not only simplifies the check but also aligns with Clojure’s idiomatic style, improving readability and avoiding redundant negation or abstraction layers.

Is this smell relevant in your opinion?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

7. Comment - Improper Emptiness Check
(Optional)

8. **Unnecessary into**

This code smell occurs when the into function is used in situations where more concise or idiomatic alternatives exist, leading to unnecessarily verbose or inefficient code. While into is useful for combining collections, it is often misused for simple type transformations—such as (into [] coll) instead of vec.

Is this smell relevant in your opinion?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes

No

I don't know

9. **Comment - Unnecessary into**
(Optional)

10. **Conditional Build-Up**

This code smell occurs when a state is incrementally constructed through a series of let, if, and assoc expressions, leading to verbose and imperative-style code. Rather than clearly expressing the transformation logic, this pattern scatters conditional state mutations across multiple branches, making it harder to reason about the overall flow.

Is this smell relevant in your opinion?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes

No

I don't know

11. **Comment - Conditional Build-Up**
(Optional)

12. **Production doall**

This code smell occurs when the doall function is used in production code to force realization of lazy sequences, often to trigger side effects or avoid deferred evaluation. While doall can be useful in REPL experimentation, its use in production undermines one of Clojure's core strengths: laziness. For large or infinite sequences, this can lead to memory spikes and unpredictable performance. In production contexts, doall often signals poor abstraction choices and should prompt reconsideration of the control flow or evaluation strategy.

Is this smell relevant in your opinion?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes

No

I don't know

13. **Comment - Production doall**
(Optional)

14. Thread Ignorance

This code smell occurs when developers avoid or misuse Clojure's threading macros (->, ->>, some->, cond->) in scenarios where they would provide clearer, more idiomatic data flow. Instead of leveraging threading to express stepwise transformations, code may fall back to repetitive bindings, deeply nested let or when-let forms, or manually sequenced function calls. This results in verbose, harder-to-follow logic and obscures the intent behind each transformation.

Is this smell relevant in your opinion?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes

No

I don't know

15. Comment - Thread Ignorance (Optional)

16. **Namespaced Keys Neglect**

This code smell occurs when developers rely on unqualified keywords (e.g., :id, :name) instead of using namespaced keywords (e.g., :user/id, :order/name). While seemingly harmless, this practice leads to ambiguity, increased risk of key collisions, and reduced semantic clarity — particularly in large or modular systems.

Is this smell relevant in your opinion?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes

No

I don't know

17. **Comment - Namespaced Keys Neglect**
(Optional)

18. **Nested Forms**

This code smell occurs when multiple binding or iteration forms—such as `let`, `when-let`, `if-let`, or `doseq`—are unnecessarily nested instead of being combined in a single, flat form. While technically valid, this nesting introduces extra indentation and structural complexity without adding semantic value. It obscures the relationships between bindings, increases visual noise, and makes the code harder to read and reason about.

Is this smell relevant in your opinion?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes

No

I don't know

19. **Comment - Nested Forms**
(Optional)

20. **Accessing non-existent Map Fields**

This code smell occurs when code accesses map keys that may not exist, relying on nil as a default return without explicit handling. In Clojure, (get m :key) returns nil both when the key is missing and when it is explicitly associated with nil, which can obscure intent and lead to subtle bugs. Since Clojure maps treat nil as both a value and a signal of absence, the distinction between "missing" and "present but empty" becomes ambiguous.

Is this smell relevant in your opinion?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

21. **Comment - Accessing non-existent Map Fields**
(Optional)

22. **Verbose Checks**

This code smell arises when developers manually implement common checks (such as checking if a number is zero, positive, or negative), when Clojure already provides clear, idiomatic functions that do the same. This results in verbose and less readable code, and misses an opportunity to leverage Clojure's built-in abstractions for clarity.

Is this smell relevant in your opinion?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes

No

I don't know

23. **Comment - Verbose Checks**

(Optional)

24. **Redundant do block**

This code smell occurs when developers wrap expressions in an explicit (do ...) block inside constructs that already support implicit sequencing, such as let, when, if, fn, try, loop, and others. This redundant use of do adds no semantic value but introduces unnecessary syntax, making the code appear more complex and imperative than it actually is.

Is this smell relevant in your opinion?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes

No

I don't know

25. **Comment - Redundant do block**
(Optional)

26. Unnecessary Macros

This code smell occurs when macros are used in situations where simpler, more conventional solutions—such as functions or existing language constructs—would suffice. While macros offer powerful metaprogramming capabilities, their overuse introduces unnecessary abstraction and complexity. This can obscure the code’s intent, make debugging more challenging and reducing maintainability.

Is this smell relevant in your opinion?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

27. Comment - Unnecessary Macros (Optional)

Functional-style Smells

These are 9 general functional programming smells that can also occur in Clojure code. These smells are not exclusive to the language but stem from overuse or misuse of functional principles such as higher-order functions, recursion, laziness, and purity.

28. **Hidden Side Effects**

This code smell occurs when functions perform side effects—such as I/O operations, state mutations, or logging—without making them explicit in their name, structure, or usage context. In functional programming, clarity around purity is essential for reasoning and testing.

Is this smell relevant in your opinion?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes

No

I don't know

29. **Comment - Hidden Side Effects**

(Optional)

30. **Inefficient Filtering**

This code smell occurs when the data generator makes excessive use of filters (such as such-that) to constrain the generated values. Instead of generating only valid values directly, the generator creates a large number of values and filters them afterward, resulting in resource waste and potential performance issues.

Is this smell relevant in your opinion?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes

No

I don't know

31. **Comment - Inefficient Filtering**
(Optional)

32. **Explicit Recursion**

This code smell occurs when explicit recursion is used instead of higher-order functions like map, reduce, or filter, which provide more concise and idiomatic solutions. Recursion should be reserved for cases where no suitable higher-level abstraction is available.

Is this smell relevant in your opinion?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes

No

I don't know

33. **Comment - Explicit Recursion**

(Optional)

34. **Positional Return Values**

This code smell occurs when functions return multiple values using positional collections such as vectors or lists, rather than explicitly labeled maps. While concise, this practice relies on the consumer to remember the semantic meaning of each position. It introduces hidden contracts and makes the code harder to read, understand, and maintain—especially as the number of return values grows.

Is this smell relevant in your opinion?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes

No

I don't know

35. **Comment - Positional Return Values**

(Optional)

36. **Deeply-nested Call Stacks**

This code smell occurs when function calls are nested to a significant depth, resulting in a long chain of execution on the stack. This makes debugging more difficult, increases the risk of stack overflow, and reduces code readability by obscuring the control flow.

Is this smell relevant in your opinion?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes

No

I don't know

37. **Comment - Deeply-nested Call Stacks**

(Optional)

38. **Overabstracted Composition**

This code smell occurs when excessive use of function composition (combining multiple functions into a single one) and partial application (fixing some arguments of a function to create a new one) makes the code overly abstract, sacrificing readability and maintainability. While function composition is a powerful tool in functional programming, overusing it can lead to deeply nested expressions that obscure the data flow.

Is this smell relevant in your opinion?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes

No

I don't know

39. **Comment - Overabstracted Composition** (Optional)

40. **Overuse Of High-Order Functions**

This code smell occurs when nearly every function takes or returns another function, leading to excessive abstraction that makes the code unnecessarily complex and harder to follow. While higher-order functions enhance flexibility and reusability, their excessive use can obscure intent, making debugging and reasoning about the code more difficult.

Is this smell relevant in your opinion?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes

No

I don't know

41. **Comment - Overuse Of High-Order Functions**
(Optional)

42. **Trivial Lambda**

This code smell occurs when anonymous functions (lambdas) are excessively used instead of named functions, reducing code clarity and reusability. This is especially problematic when lambda expressions are chained or become overly complex, making the code harder to read, understand, and maintain.

Is this smell relevant in your opinion?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes

No

I don't know

43. **Comment - Trivial Lambda**
(Optional)

44. **Lazy Side Effects**

This code smell occurs when side effects (such as state changes or external interactions) happen within lazy evaluated code. Since lazy evaluation delays computation until needed, these side effects may not execute as expected, leading to unpredictable behavior and making the code harder to debug and maintain.

Is this smell relevant in your opinion?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes

No

I don't know

45. **Comment - Lazy Side Effects**

(Optional)

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